

POLITICAL SCIENCES

THE DEVELOPMENT OF NEW WORK MECHANISMS FOR CENTRAL AND LOCAL PUBLIC INSTITUTIONS AS FORMULAS OF MAKING THE INTERNAL MANAGERIAL CONTROL SYSTEMS BETTER

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Abstract

The efficient spending of public funds and the constant reform of the public administration constitutes the basis of an efficient management in public institutions. So, in order to reach the goals set, it is necessary to implement a system of internal management control that offers safety to the leader of the institution in order for him to achieve his goals economically, efficiently and effectively.

The purpose of this article is to showcase the importance of an internal managerial control system as an instrument of preventing and overcoming problems in achieving goals in realising objectives on one side, and innovative solutions in implementing this instrument in public entities, on the otherside.

The theoretical basis and the research constituted the basis of designing a web application that can be considered a vital function of internal managerial control in public institutions.

Keywords: internal managerial control, innovative solutions, digitalization, safety, risk

INTRODUCTION

The changes that take place constantly in the social, economic and politic environment draw new trajectories that constitute the basis of the reform of the public administration. We can consider that the internal managerial control is an important trajectory, made up from rules and general principles of good practice, accepted on both national and international levels, determined by the legislative and administrative context. It is important to understand the internal control as a managerial function, not as a verification function or a function of control.

The methods to organise and implement internal managerial control in public establishments is mainly regulated in The Government's Ordinance number 119/1999 concerning internal control/ managerial and preventive financial control, reissued with ulterior changes and additions, The Government's Emergency Ordinance number 86/2014 concerning the determination of methods of reorganising central public administration and the changes and additions brought to other laws, approved with changes and additions through Law number 174/2015, with ulterior changes, in connection with The Government's General Secretariat Ordinance number 600/2018 concerning the approval of the Code for internal managerial control in public institutions.

The internal control system is the responsibility of the public institution's leader as he needs to implement, adapt and develop the system so that it becomes a mechanism that determines institutions to ensure that their activity is consistent with the goals and the purposes of the allocated resources, having a correct evaluation of associated risks made by the assigned entities in order to identify vulnerabilities by establishing adequate measures to eliminate them.

Considering the aspects mentioned above, by theoretical substantiation and research, I have identified the need to create another meaning for the internal managerial control term, by creating an innovative software whose role is to offer safety for the institutions and also to ensure that the public funds are managed in an economical, efficient and effective way.

This paperwork describes a solution for digitalization, with maximal performances and minimal resources, regarding the implementation of a part of internal control.

THE ORGANISATION OF PUBLIC FINANCIAL CONTROL IN ROMANIA

According to its definition, the public financial control represents "*the entire public internal control system, made up of public institutions' control systems, Government structures' systems and the systems of entities responsible with harmonizing and implementing principles and standards of control and audit.*"¹

By joining the European Union and by adopting the communautaire acquis, our country took the responsibility to make the conceptual and strategic context of the public financial control better and to implement a viable system of public financial control that includes all the public entities and authorities, receiving control and evaluation responsibilities in order to identify any misconducts regarding the goals that were set on one way, and to analyse the causes that determined the misconducts on the other hand, so that preventive and remedial measures are applied.

This approach can be found in strategies developed by the Government, where the Ministry of Public Finances has the main role, as a specialised central authority of public administration, responsible with creating and implementing policies regarding the financial control and the management of financial resources.

¹ The Romanian Parliament, Law number 672/2002 regarding the public audit, reissued, with ulterior changes

The Ministry of Public Finances coordinates a series of entities of control and specialised structures nationally, their mission being given by the evaluation of the method of organising financial resources and by the financial control, and also by enacting the type of random control in order to ensure that the financial laws are respected by the public institutions.

According to the “*Public strategy of financial control in Romania for the 2014-2016 time period*”,² the architecture of financial public control in our country has the following structure:

Financial public control

A. External financial public control enforced by:

- a) Structures of the Government;
- b) Other control authorities in central public administration.

B. Internal financial public control enforced by:

- a) The control of the Parliament;
- b) Romanian Court of Accounts.

INTERNAL FINANCIAL PUBLIC CONTROL

In The International Organization of Supreme Audit Institutions (INTOSAI), the internal financial public control is considered “*an integrated process led by the institution’s management and by the personnel, conceived in order to approach the risks and to offer safety in the implementation of the institution’s missions, by achieving the following objectives: performing operations in an organised, ethical, economical and efficient way, fulfilling responsibilities, respecting laws and regulations, protecting resources against losses and against the prejudices and the misconducts.*”³

This approach was adopted by the Romanian legislation and adapted so that the internal financial public control is defined as “*the entire public internal control system, made up of public institutions’ control systems, Government structures’ systems and the systems of entities responsible with harmonizing and implementing principles and standards of control and audit.*”⁴

In other words, the internal financial public control encapsulates all forms of control that can be enforced in public entities, in concordance with the principles and the control standards that exist and that are regulated by laws, which are internal public audit, preventive financial control, financial management control, the internal managerial control system and the financial and economic inspection.

EXTERNAL FINANCIAL PUBLIC CONTROL

The external financial public control is enforced by the Parliament or by the Court of Accounts.

The Parliament is the entity responsible with adopting annual financial laws and correction laws created by the Executive. The parliamentary control is made in plenary or separately, by every Room, using all forms and means regarding control, such as the control enforced by messages, reports, inquiries, programmes

that were presented to the Parliament, the control enforced by parliamentary committees, the control enforced by questions and interpretations, the right of the deputies and Senate members to ask and obtain information, the control enforced by The People’s Lawyer.⁵

From this perspective, the control of the Parliament is headed towards the approval of the public budget and also of the budget execution, as well as adopting votes for the retraction of trust given to the Government in case of identifying problems.

As far as the Romanian Court of Accounts is concerned, it represents an institution that functions autonomously and the legal context of its activities is set by the 140th article of the Romanian Constitution and by the Law number 94/1992 regarding the organisation and functioning of the Romanian Court of Accounts, reissued and modified by the Law number 77/2022.

According to the definitions in the studies in this domain, “*the control attributions of the Romanian Court of Accounts are enforced on the method of formation, administration and use of the financial resources of the public environment, as well as the manner that the public and private patrimony of the state and of the administrative units is managed by the public entities, with accent on the concordance between the real state determined by the financial inspectors and the situation regulated by the law.*”⁶

Observing the attributions that the Romanian Court of Accounts has, it becomes clear that this institution is very important in preventing and identifying fraud and corruption. This form of control is a teaching task because it forms, strengthens and develops the professional ethic of those who work in the field of managing public funds.

Being the supreme audit institution, it represents Romania in the international organisations in this domain. In order to fulfill as many obligations in the external audit fields, in its quality of member state in the European Union, Romania created the Audit Authority, with responsibilities regarding non-refundable funds given to Romania by the European Union. In the administrative units, the tasks of the Court are fulfilled by the Chambers of Accounts, that can be found in every county and in Bucharest, and that don’t have legal personality.

THE INTERNAL MANAGERIAL CONTROL – THE MAIN INSTRUMENT OF EVALUATION OF THE PROGRESS OR REGRESS IN REACHING OBJECTIVES

In public institutions, the internal control activity is of great importance, mainly because by fulfilling a set of default measures, the quality of the activity in the institution is validated.

Over the years, in order to ensure an efficient management, the public institutions have become more and

² The Ministry of Public Finances, “The development strategy of the internal public financial control in Romania for the 2014-2016 time period”, January 2014, Appendix 1

³ The Ministry of Public Finances, “The development strategy of the internal public financial control in Romania for the 2014-2016 time period”, January 2014, Appendix 1

⁴ The Romanian Parliament, Law number 672/2002 regarding the public audit, Chapter I, General provisions, Art. 2, letter h)

⁵ <https://www.senat.ro/pagini/control/control.htm>

⁶ Roman, Constantin, Public Financial Control Teaching Material, Economic Studies Academy, Faculty of Finances, Insurance, Banks and Stock Exchange, European Public Governance Masters

more preoccupied by the implementation of their own internal control system.

In spite of that, the creation of such an institutional frame has its roots in the United States of America, where, in 1985, Senator Treadway established the National Commission on Fraudulent Financial Reporting with the responsibility to follow the activity of internal control and the role that it plays in an institution. After that, Committee of Sponsoring Organizations of the Treadway Commission was created, also known as COSO, who launched, in 1992, the Internal Control — Integrated Framework.

In the beginning, this was used just for the private environment but, through the years, it was applied to the public environment as well.

Initially, the internal control concept according to COSO was targetting four fundamental principles, such as:

1. *The internal control is a total process, not an extracurricular activity, it's meant to reach an objective, and not a goal;*
2. *The internal control is enforced by people which makes it imperfect, it doesn't represent just political manuals, forms and documents, but also the people on every level of the organisation;*
3. *The internal control can provide the management a reasonable insurance on the fact that the organisation's objectives will be fulfilled;*
4. *The internal control takes part in fulfilling the organisation's objectives.*⁷

In 2000, in the European Union was published a document called "The White Book of managerial reform in the European Commission services", a document that imposed the European community, once the external financial help is approved, to ensure the enforcing of the principles in the White Book by implementing a single control frame for all the structures in the public environment, as a validation instrument of the way that the funds are managed.

Because of the time that passed and the development of new technologies, the set of principles was revised and adapted, as the institutions in the public environment were always looking to make the management of their activities better, the character of the implemented measures through managerial control becoming increasingly complex.

THE LEGISLATION CONCERNING INTERNAL MANAGERIAL CONTROL IN ROMANIA

The Ordinance number 119/1999 regarding the internal managerial control and the preventive financial control, reissued with the ulterior changes and additions, was created in order to regulate this kind of activity taking place in the public entities on a national level, the main goal being the tracking of the "efficient, effective and economical way in which the public funds and the public patrimony are managed."⁸

Regardless, the enforcements of the standards concerning the internal managerial control became possible just after the Order of de Ministry of Public Finances number 946/2005 was issued, approving the "Internal Control Code" and containing the management and internal control standards in public entities and foreseeing the development of the internal managerial control systems.

The need to improve the internal managerial control activity in the public environment imposed new changes and additional provisions in the legislative frame, respectively:

- Law number 174/2015 for the approval of the Emergency Ordinance of the Government number 86/2014 regarding the establishment of reorganising methods for the central public administration and the changing and amending some laws;
- The Government's General Secretariat Order number 600/2018 regarding the approval of the internal managerial control of public entities.

In general, the notion of internal managerial control refers to the activity of constant evaluation of the operations that are being made in a public entity, with the help of a set of instruments of management compatible with the subordinated structures, in hopes of obtaining control over the activities in an institution, representing at the same time a model of evaluation and verification of the ability to achieve performance in concordance with the desired objectives.

In spite of the relevance that it has, the internal managerial control activity has its limitations, which come from problems that are often hard to manage.

So, in every institution, this type of activity offers a vast evaluation, but not an absolute one, facing challenges like:

- A series of changes manifested both internally and externally which have an influence on the public institution's activity;
- Mistakes risen from wrong estimations, that don't match with the current realities, workplace negligence caused by the personnel, as well as different types of inadvertences and omissions;
- The personnel being influenced by the management or by other employees when fulfilling their work attributions;
- Elaborating new control procedures that haven't been implemented or were partially omitted.

Over time, in Romania, the public financial control system has suffered a series of changes, being adapted with the help of some legislative measures relative to the existing possibilities and challenges. Considering all of this, it is clear that the system must be consolidated and improved with a series of measures like:

- Improving the legislative frame of the public financial control by adapting it to the European standards and current practices;

⁷ The Government's General Secretariat, 2019 Report regarding the stage of implementing internal managerial control systems in public institutions that constitute main credit authorising officers of state budget, social insurance budget and any special fund budget

⁸ The Romanian Government, Ordinance number 119 from August 31th 1999 (reissues) regarding internal control and preventive financial control

- The need to train the employees of the public environment with the help of some classes held by specialists;
- Integrating financial control in the domain of internal managerial control.

CASE STUDY: DEVELOPING AN IT SYSTEM AS AN INSTRUMENT TO RESPOND TO THE NECESSITIES OF MAKING THE ENFORCEMENT OF INTERNAL MANAGERIAL CONTROL MEASURES BETTER

The need to make the fulfillment of measures and recommendations imposed by competent entities to the public institutions more efficient after the audit/financial control is enforced has led to identifying some good formulas that can track the stage of implementation.

Ensuring a good management of the public institutions in Romania by imposing a new set of instruments from the internal managerial control field in order to remove the limitations manifested by the personnel in the public administration, according to the issues laid out before and ensuring that the performance goals are reached in concordance with the desired objectives have become a constant concern for the author as he was conducting his research for the final thesis.

To this end, developing a system that allows the management of a public institution to strictly follow the stage of the implementation of the set objectives with the help of the reports issued by the structures that are competent to conduct audit and control missions, after

their activity is over, was transposed by developing an IT system in the form of a web application that responds to these kind of needs and to the current context regarding digitalization.

In the present case, the functionality of the platform is centred around the flux of administrative documents uploaded by the users. These fluxes are consisted of a series of justifying documents that represent the basis of the implementation of measures and recommendations imposed and, if it is necessary, the unique number of the file. In concordance with the information in the flux, the users get notifications in order to help them respect the deadlines imposed by the control entities for implementing the orders.

The application responds to the needs that the public institutions have regarding the digitalization process and ensures the manager of the public entity that the activities of implementing the recommended measures are legal, regular, economic, effective and efficient.

In the following pages we will present different elements regarding the soft's interface and the information integrated in the soft, keeping in mind the fact that the data referring to the user are just examples, sustaining our effort to better illustrate the functionalities.

The welcome page (Homepage) – The application is in the form of a web programme, allowing the users to access it anytime, from any device available. The access is permitted by creating an account for every user.

Page – Institution – In this page the identifying data of the public entity are introduced. In the situation where the public entity has a subordinated institution, in this page a selection can be done so that the main credit authorising officer can visualise the information uploaded in the application. The main credit authorising officer has only the possibility to see the document,

and doesn't have the right to edit or input additional information.

The data uploaded by each institution are confidential, the access to the information being set very clear in the beginning, when the contract is signed.

Gestionare date instituție Editează informații

Nume Instituție publica - SIRAR	Adresa strada, nr. Judet Ilfov, România
CUI 123456	Instituție ordonatoare Încă nu ați setat o instituție ordonatoare.

Prin selectarea unei instituții ordonatoare veți permite unei instituții să vă urmărească rapoartele CCR și monitorizările, împreună cu măsurile acestora. Instituția ordonatoare nu va putea edita nicio informație ce aparține acestei instituții.

Page – Control reports – In this page the control reports are uploaded, the related Decisions, if there is necessary, and the Follow-up reports. The purpose of this page is to incorporate the documents issued by the control and audit entities, grouped by Report, ensuring the swiftness in accessing and visualising them at any-time, from any device, eliminating the bureaucracy. The

application isn't just about de Report of the Court of Accounts, because every institution can upload internal audit reports, reports from the Control Body of the institution that coordinates its activity, reports from the Control Body of the Prime Minister, etc.

Gestionare rapoarte de control Adaugă raport

Ați introdus 18 rapoarte.

caută... Sortare după dată

Raport Curtea de Conturi nr 123 introdus pe 17 August 2021	Documente încărcate
Raport Curtea de Conturi nr 123 introdus pe 17 August 2021	Documente încărcate
Raport curtea de conturi introdus pe 17 August 2021	Documente încărcate

Page – Managing monitoring – A collection of recommendations/measures are incorporated in this page, regarding every report/decision. Every monitoring has its own recommendations/measures.

Gestionare monitorizari Crează monitorizare nouă

Ați început 3 monitorizari.

caută... Sortare după dată

Monitorizarea BAZA SPORTIVA cu numărul 4 creată pe 17 August 2021 Au fost adăugate 0 fișiere și 5 măsuri din care 1 a expirat.	Detalii
Monitorizarea Masura 1 cu numărul 109070 creată pe 17 August 2021 Au fost adăugate 1 fișier și 2 măsuri din care niciuna nu a expirat.	Detalii

For the purpose of drawing clear responsibilities and terms regarding de fulfillment of the established goals, every recommendation receives a series of data

and documents, such as the number of the measure/recommendation (for an accurate monitoring and for a precise identification of the measure/recommendation),

the text of the measure/recommendation, the implementation term, the extended term (if there was a discussion with the control entity regarding this problem and if there is a justifying document), the status of the measure, the people responsible with implementing the

measure, observations. All the justifying documents are uploaded in this section.

As a consequence, the manager of the institution receives the information regarding the actions that are being taken in real time, so that the communication process in the institution is more effective.

These pages represent the foundation of the SIRAR application and also the foundation of an efficient and effective management in following the measures/recommendations issued by the control and audit entities.

The main goal of the application is to shelter the main credit authorising officer by monitoring the deadlines of the obligations that he has in implementing the measures/recommendations issued after the control activities are conducted and in respecting the deadlines enforced by the court.

Why did we choose the safety term?

The answer couldn't be more simple because the consequences of not fulfilling the measures imposed by the Court of Accounts, not recovering the prejudices by not following and not enforcing the measures imposed by the Court of Accounts are either represented by a civil fine or they can constitute a crime that can be punished by either a fine or by jail time between 3 months and 1 year.

So, the SIRAR application allows the management of the public entity to follow, in real time and with precision, the fulfillment of the objectives that were set, with the purpose of implementing the measures/recommendations imposed after the internal and external control activities have been conducted.

As far as the control and monitoring of the legality and regularity concerning the use of public funds, the main and secondary credit authorising officers can have access, in real time, to the documents issued by the control and audit entities as well as the internal documents elaborated with the purpose of implementing measures/recommendations imposed for the subordinated institutions.

Page – Accounts – Every institution can create a minimum of 3 accounts, 1 main account that belongs to the leader of the institution and 2 secondary accounts that will manage the application.

Page – Notifications – Based on the information uploaded in the application, the users receive notifications as explained below:

- Notifications regarding the stage of implementation of the measures/recommendation imposed by the control entities – 15, 30, 60, 90 days;
- Notifications about the court terms that were set – 15, 30, 60, 90 days;

- Notifications about the summarised solution, on the day that it is published;
- Notifications about the date when the Court of Accounts will begin the control activity over the institution;
- Monthly notifications called “Progress Report”, send via e-mail, regarding the stage of the implementation of the measures/recommendations.

All of these notifications have the role to inform the manager of the institution regarding the actions that have been taken in order to fulfil the tasks that were given, the status of the measure/recommendation and the legal situation of these measures, if needed. Everything helps the leader of the institution to act in a preventive manner in order to implement the measures/recommendations or to ask for an extension of the deadline if it is necessary.

Page – Legislation – This section has the role to offer every institution the possibility to create its own Legislative Library and, with the fluxes concerning the monitoring, to improve the operational efficiency, the communication and the interinstitutional transparency, including the reduction of the document processing costs.

Page – Managing the institutions – Considering the main credit authorising officers’ obligation to ensure the legal, regular, economical, efficient and effective credit distribution to the subordinated institutions, the

application allows the monitoring of the reports and of the actions taken by the subordinated institutions in order to implement the measures/recommendations imposed by the control entities.

Another important functionality of the software is represented by the chat module, which allows the public workers or the contractual personnel to communicate permanently with the SIRAR representatives, so that the implementation time of the application is as reduced and as efficient as possible.

EXPECTED RESULTS

The use of the SIRAR application constitutes an important key in the management process, the principles that result from it being

- Implementing the measures imposed from the audit and control organs in time;

- Keeping the leader of the institution permanently informed about the real situation in the institution he manages;
- Efficiently managing the resources in the process of implementing the measures imposed after the control and audit missions;
- The application creates all the premises for the management of an institution to fulfil its obligations imposed according to the control missions;
- Achieving the goals set in an economic, efficient and effective manner;
- Monitoring and controlling the use of the public funds in a legal and regular manner.

CONCLUSIONS

The novelty characteristic of this kind of system comes from the uniqueness of the mechanism that allows the management of the public institutions to remove the omissions, the ineffective time and resource management in implementing the measures imposed by the control/audit entities.

The annual reports of the Court of Accounts stipulate that “the inquiries made by the Court of Accounts’ auditors provide sufficient aspects that require improvements in order to make from the internal managerial control system an useful goal-reaching instrument.”⁹

The use of this instrument was implemented so that it is easy to manage, allowing the employees of the

⁹ The Romanian Court of Accounts, The public report for 2018, December 2019, Bucharest

public institutions to respect the deadlines for the obligations imposed to them. The notifications that are sent to the users, announcing the upcoming deadlines or the upcoming visit from the Court of Accounts, the legislation that applies to this domain, which can be found within the application, are all creating the premises for the management of the institution to fulfil all the obligations that are imposed, according to the measures that have been given to them.

Another important advantage of the SIRAR application is that it is meant to support the public entities in the digitalization process and in the process of removing all the flaws in the traditional bureaucratic system, a change that brings with it new elements into the public management by making the activity and the communication in the institution more efficient.

The application incorporates essential functionalities of internal managerial control by having clearly drawn objectives, by having a plan, by diminishing risks, by communicating and by containing fluxes of documents, becoming a real support system for achieving goals while respecting deadlines.

This way, any leader of a public institution involved in the decision-making process, must always know the situation that the institution is in regarding the control and audit missions that took place, which sometimes is hard to accomplish without having a really good plan.

From this perspective, the advantage of using the soft comes from the improvement of risk management in public institutions in Romania, with significant consequences over the results, by developing this instrument in the internal managerial control system field.

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